

MARBURGUM

Time Machine Marburg

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Time Line

The figure above illustrates the project pipeline. Although a significant portion of the work was dedicated to data cleaning — which will be discussed in detail in the following sections — the entire workflow and outcomes are summarized in the diagram above.

1. Introduction

The "Time Machine Marburg" project aims to analyze and organize a complex and "untidy" dataset consisting of historical images, objects, landscapes, maps, and texts related to the city of Marburg. This interdisciplinary project combines AI and Art history. We have used machine learning techniques to gain a better understanding of the Dataset, clean the Dataset (create a structured taxonomy of the historical data), and cluster images into "building" and "not building". The outcomes are intended to help structure the originally messy dataset and to support future research and public engagement with Marburg's rich cultural heritage.

The project's primary objectives include:

1. Cleaning and organizing the dataset for analysis.
2. Clustering images based on visual similarity and classification based on metadata and a new dataset of handpicked images and accurate labels.
3. Developing a scalable methodology for linking and visualizing data.
4. Suggesting ideas and suggestions for future research directions.

For this project, different tools are used: from Visual Studio and Excel to Trello and Telegram for better project management.

2. Dataset Overview

The dataset comprises numerous types of images, including historical photos, blueprints, and textual metadata, offering the potential to study Marburg's architectural and cultural history.

In the schema above, you can see how the archive we worked with is structured. We found out that the structure of the archive is made of different items, which we refer to as objects: e.g., Building, Maps, Scans, Plates, Portraits, Artworks, etc. Each object can have different parts, which are subcategories of the object, and each part has an image or images related to it. For example, an old paper can be an object, part 1 can be one side of it, and part 2 can be the other side of it.

Each image has an archive link. That link leads to a unique page for the image. It should be emphasized that each page is related to an object, and each object can have multiple pages related to it.

As it is obvious, the data we are working with is highly complicated, and that has caused challenges, which are mentioned in the Challenges and Solutions section.

2.1. Dataset Composition

In our dataset, we left the following columns. We decided to work with both original images and their scans, and without blueprints. The information below is about **images only, without blueprints**. Because when both scan and image exist, they are identical.

Column Name	Type	UNIQUE	Description
<code>id_record</code>	LINK	NO	A link to an object (e.g. set of papers of a book)
<code>id_persistent</code>	LINK	YES	A link to a subobject of an object (e.g. one sheet of paper from this book). Sometimes is similar to <code>record identifiers</code>
<code>label</code>	TEXT	NO	A label, text description
<code>image_links</code>	SET OF LINKS	YES (?)	A set of links to download all corresponding images to this subobject (e.g. all sides of this sheet of paper in each link)
<code>microfiche_links</code>	SET OF LINKS	YES (?)	A link to download pictures from archive. Probably there are scans of original objects, books, photos of sculptures with metadata on them. Could be used as a style transfer and metadata resource, if it is not in the <code>identification labels</code> column

Our first task was to do the Image clustering of all objects without blueprints:

- 34712 archive objects (sculpture, book, photos, plans, architecture plan of buildings)
- 36981 images to work on (scans and originals; without blueprints)
- Average number of pictures per object: **2.63**
- Median: **1.0**
- Max: **829** & Min: **0**

2.1.1. Missing labels

For the missing values in labels (NO_LABEL or Ohne Titel), the images are not relevant, and after all are downloaded and visually checked, we omitted them from the dataset.

In the whole dataset:

- Number of missing labels: 62 (0.16%)
- Images to download among them: 62 (0.11%)
- Scans to download among them: 26

Without Blueprints:

- Number of missing labels: 56 (0.147%)
- Images to download among them: 49 (0.16%)
- Scans to download among them: 26

2.1.2. Unique labels

The number of Unique labels is 29102. And the unique labels without blueprints is 20163

Frequency	Label
548	Wohnhaus
375	Wohn- und Geschäftshaus
350	Grabstein
135	Krug
106	Serie von Marburger Wandfliesen Serie von Marburger Wa
101	Bodenfliesen Bodenfliesen/Bodenfliese
100	Wandfliesengruppe Wandfliesengruppe/Wandfliese
92	Grabstein Grabstein/Rückseite
87	Grabstein Grabstein/Vorderseite
83	Negativ (Fotografie)
82	Kaffeekanne
75	Straße
74	Vase
70	Sogenannte Trümmerkampagne: Fotografen bei der Arbeit
68	Photographie: Das Gebirge "Hohe Tauern".
67	Teller
64	Schüssel
55	Ohne Titel
45	Photographie: Landschaft bei Semmering
43	Truhe
41	Photographie: Die Zillertaler Alpen
...	

Also, **objects without any images** for consideration (3488 pcs.) are deleted. However, it could be added to the label analysis.

As it is demonstrated in the image, *id_persistent* is equal to *id_record* with “?part=N” in the end, which points to the ordinal number of the object. Missing values in *id_persistent* are generated this way.

2.1.3 MVP Dataset

As mentioned before, one image might belong to multiple objects, and one object may consist of duplicated links:

```
df_mvp['link'].value_counts().head(5)
```

```
link
http://www.bildindex.de/bilder/d/fmd463147    20
http://www.bildindex.de/bilder/d/fmd463144    20
http://www.bildindex.de/bilder/d/fmd463146    20
http://www.bildindex.de/bilder/d/fmd463149    18
http://www.bildindex.de/bilder/d/fmd463148    18
Name: count, dtype: int64
```

```
for ind,obj in df_mvp.iterrows():
    if obj.link == 'http://www.bildindex.de/bilder/d/fmd463140':
        print(obj.id, obj.file_name, dict_labels_reversed[obj.id_label])
```

```
8447-22 img-0002061779-fmd463140 Landgrafenschloss Landgrafenschloss/Leutehaus
8447-81 img-0002061779-fmd463140 Landgrafenschloss Landgrafenschloss/Leutehaus
8448-11 img-0002061837-fmd463140 Landgrafenschloss Landgrafenschloss/Leutehaus Landgrafenschloss/Leutehaus/Keller
8449-11 img-0001602481-fmd463140 Landgrafenschloss Landgrafenschloss/Leutehaus Landgrafenschloss/Leutehaus/Keller
8456-24 img-0002075429-fmd463140 Landgrafenschloss Landgrafenschloss/Leutehaus Landgrafenschloss/Leutehaus/Dachge
8457-11 img-0002075430-fmd463140 Landgrafenschloss Landgrafenschloss/Leutehaus Landgrafenschloss/Leutehaus/Dachge
34710-479 img-0001350452-fmd463140 Landgrafenschloss
34710-538 img-0001350452-fmd463140 Landgrafenschloss
```

- For the MVP dataset, we are interested only in unique links to image, filename, and tags (outdoor, indoor, etc.)
- However, it could be crucial to have a connection to the object in the archive and all the lists of possible labels.
- The problem was that one image belonged to different similar labels and objects (different parts of the castle, which are stored as different objects in the archive)

Then, we decided to create a dataset with unique links and related file names (first appearance). We saved the opportunity to create a dataset with all links in “images.csv”, which can be found on our GitHub project. From this unique list of links, we downloaded the images. And the updated number of pictures is **36981**.

“id” of an object in “dataset_CLEAN.csv”:

	link	id_objects	labels	file_name	id
0	http://www.bildindex.de/bilder/d/ae00001b05	[9077]	[1617]	scn-ae00001b05	ae00001b05
1	http://www.bildindex.de/bilder/d/ae00001b06	[9077]	[1617]	scn-ae00001b06	ae00001b06
2	http://www.bildindex.de/bilder/d/ae00001b07	[9077]	[1617]	scn-ae00001b07	ae00001b07
3	http://www.bildindex.de/bilder/d/ae00001b0				

	id	label
0	0	Lauenhain (Kreis Hainichen), Fahnenträger eine...
1	1	Fenster (Bauelement)
2	2	Kassel, Infanteriekasernen an der Königsstraße...
3	3	Waldeck, Domäne, Wohnhaus, Umbauentwurf, Aufrisse
4	4	Kassel, Opernhaus (Altes Hoftheater), Aborte i...

2.2. Data Cleaning

In summary:

- Removed 3,488 objects without any associated images.
- Missing values in labels: only 62 (0.16%).
- Unique labels (no blueprints): 20,163.
- Rearrange values: in IDs, missing images, and missing labels.

3. Methodology

In this section, we have the steps for our project in chronological order.

3.1. Data Preprocessing

As a summary, we did these steps for Data Preprocessing:

1. **Deduplication:**
 - Ensured unique links to images, filenames, and tags.

2. Missing Data Handling:

- Generated IDs for objects with missing id_persistent.
- Deleted HTML pages without images.

3. Image Rescaling

- Original images were rescaled to 224x224 pixels, achieving 95% optimization in storage usage.
- Resulting dataset size: 500 MB (from 11.5 GB).

1710x1200 px, 581 Kb

224x224 px, 15 Kb

3.2. Clustering

The final goal of this section is to separate “buildings” from “non-buildings” and later, focusing on “buildings” clusters, separate “Outdoor” clusters from others. This way, we have a more detailed, structured dataset and can also focus only on Outdoor buildings.

The first attempt is trying a variational autoencoder model, where we encoded images into a 256-dimensional latent space to enable clustering. Key parameters and architectural details:

- Encoder: Six convolutional layers with LeakyReLU activations.
- Decoder: Six transposed convolutional layers with tanh activation.
- Latent space: 256 dimensions.

We deliberately excluded variational autoencoders (VAEs) from the final pipeline after observing subpar reconstruction performance during initial experiments. More critically, there remains an unresolved question in the literature as to whether a general-purpose VAE trained from scratch can effectively capture high-level semantic representations required for clustering tasks, particularly when compared to feature extractors from pretrained convolutional neural networks such as ResNet50, VGG16, AlexNet, or MobileNet. These pretrained models, having been optimized on large-scale datasets like ImageNet, offer robust and semantically rich feature embeddings that are better suited for downstream tasks such as visual clustering and classification in limited-data regimes.

Results of Encoder and Decoder:

- **ResNet and K-means:**

After facing technical obstacles for the VAE model, we applied a feature extraction model with ResNet. Then, K-means was applied on the feature space vectors, and the result of this method was satisfactory. Through our code, the system processes a batch of images by first loading each image and preparing it through resizing, color adjustment, and normalization to match the input requirements of the learning model (this part is shortened by prior resizing of the dataset separately to 224x224). Once prepared, each image is passed through a pre-trained model (ResNet) operating in inference mode to extract a compact and high-level feature representation. These extracted feature vectors, which encode the visual (and semantic) information of the images, are collected into a feature list. After processing all images, a clustering algorithm (K-means from Python's "sklearn.cluster") is applied to the feature list, grouping visually or semantically similar images together based on their feature similarities.

- **Clustering Results:**

- We have tested different cluster numbers: 20, 50, 70, 100.

- We were satisfied with 100, judging by the visualization of the first 99 samples and further inspection (separating into folders in regard to their clusters and inspecting each folder). The size of the clusters influenced the number of clusters we chose.

Here, you can see the number of image instances in each cluster for 100 clusters:

Using 100 clusters made it:

- Easier to judge a cluster when its size (number of images) is less than 1000.
- Easier for humans to describe a cluster in a couple of words.

- More detailed in clustering, therefore, more potential for future work with portraits and postcards.
- Disadvantage: more clusters to consider.

We decided to stick to photos only and primarily exterior.

Next, we created a thumbnail for each cluster, including 224 random images from the corresponding cluster, facilitating human and AI observation. two examples from two different clusters, thumbnails are provided below:

The left thumbnail belongs to the 10th cluster (which is named “Mixed Artworks Archive”), and the thumbnail on the right belongs to cluster 5 (Historical Church Facades).

3.2.1. Observations:

Among different objects, we had to consider visible features such as architectural and non-architectural concepts, black-and-white or colorful images, the existence of maps, and scans.

- E.g., Clusters 7 and 87 exhibited concepts of architecture (e.g., schemas and 3D models), and Cluster 9 reflected medieval architectural concepts.
- With Scans, shortcut learning might arise due to the specific format of images (in white frame with text). However, in most cases, the pattern within the clusters remains:

3.2.2. Prompt engineering for ChatGPT taxonomy

At this step, first, we gave all 100 thumbnails to our LLM of choice (ChatGPT) and asked it to name them.

Here is the prompt:

```

EXAMPLE OUTPUT
Cluster Name: Architectural Blueprints
Key Words: buildings, floor plans, elevations, annotations, technical drawings
Detailed Description: The visualization contains detailed technical drawings of buildings, including floor plans, elevations, and structural details. The lines are precise, and the documents have a dated, historical appearance suggesting early 20th-century architecture. Most of the pictures are in black and white.

WHAT NOT TO DO
1. NEVER EXCEED 3 WORDS FOR THE CLUSTER NAME.
2. DO NOT INCLUDE PERSONAL OPINIONS OR SUBJECTIVE INTERPRETATIONS.
3. AVOID VAGUE DESCRIPTIONS LIKE "MISCELLANEOUS IMAGES" OR "VARIOUS OBJECTS."
4. DO NOT SPECULATE ABOUT IMAGE SOURCES OR CONTENT UNLESS VISUALLY APPARENT.
5. NEVER OMIT A CLUSTER NAME OR DETAILED DESCRIPTION OR KEY WORDS.

FINAL REMARKS
1. ENSURE HIGH ACCURACY IN BOTH THE NAME AND DESCRIPTION.
2. PRIORITIZE VISUAL CLARITY IN YOUR ANALYSIS.
3. FOLLOW THE PROVIDED EXAMPLES AS A TEMPLATE FOR YOUR RESPONSES.
</system_prompt>

```

Some of the criteria for this prompt are:

- Conciseness
- Maximum accuracy of description
- Loyalty to the original content and no AI ideation
- Vivid descriptions

The output example:

Cluster Name: "Church Ceilings and Stained-Glass Windows"

Description:

This cluster focuses on detailed architectural and artistic elements found in churches, particularly ceilings and stained-glass windows. The images prominently feature intricate ribbed vaults, elaborate tracery, decorative bosses, and various ceiling patterns typical of Gothic and Renaissance styles. Vibrant stained-glass windows showcase religious figures, geometric designs, and floral motifs, adding a rich palette of colors. The cluster also includes aerial and upward perspectives, emphasizing the grandeur and complexity of these architectural features.

Cluster #98

We went further than our MVP with data for future researchers and flexibility for them.

Next step, we asked LLM (Chat GPT) to extract the clusters related to outdoor images. Then we cross-checked the results with human agent. After that, for the purpose of the project, we divided the dataset into Images related to: Indoor, Outdoor, People, and Details.

Here, we checked the accuracy of ChatGPT according to the results of human observation for outdoor clusters:

Correctly Matched Clusters (True Positives): 10

Incorrectly Selected by AI (False Positives): 4

Clusters Missed by AI (False Negatives): 4

True results by human agent (Number of cluster): [0, 1, 4, 5, 12, 22, 33, 40, 49, 65, 66, 74, 83, 99]

Result by AI (Number of cluster): [0, 5, 6, 12, 22, 29, 33, 35, 40, 49, 51, 66, 83, 99]

Correct Selection Percentage (How well AI matched human results) → 71.43%

3.3. Metadata

During our research on the dataset, we noticed that in the HTML, there is useful information: address, type of object, and date.

The screenshot shows the BILDINDEX website interface. At the top, there is a search bar with the text 'Suchbegriff eingeben' and a magnifying glass icon. Below the search bar, there is a navigation bar with 'zur Trefferliste' and '1 von 1 Treffern'. The main content area features a photograph of a window frame on the left and a list of metadata on the right. The metadata includes 'Standort: Ronhausen, Bauernhaus, 14', 'Datierung: 1701/1800', 'Gattung: Angewandte Kunst', 'Sammlung: Marburg, Museum für Kunst und Kultur Marburg, Inventar-Nr. 392', 'Objekt-PID: http://id.bildindex.de/thing/000167773', 'Link zu dieser Seite: https://www.bildindex.de/document/ob', and 'Datensatz von: Bildarchiv Foto Marburg'. The date '1701/1800' is circled in red.

Standort:	Ronhausen, Bauernhaus, 14
Datierung:	1701/1800
Gattung:	Angewandte Kunst
Sammlung:	Marburg, Museum für Kunst und Kultur Marburg, Inventar-Nr. 392
Objekt-PID:	http://id.bildindex.de/thing/000167773
Link zu dieser Seite:	https://www.bildindex.de/document/ob
Datensatz von:	Bildarchiv Foto Marburg

By scraping all links of objects, we obtained rather descriptive metadata for 99% of objects.

Knowing the list of university buildings addresses from Wikidata of UniMarburg, we have chosen relevant objects:

34 university addresses were found, which are the most used buildings.

Here you can check the list of the Number of images for each Uni-address and building addresses respectively:

- 396 Marburg, Biegenstraße 11
- 318 Marburg, Deutschhausstraße 9
- 195 Marburg, Lahntor 3
- 39 Marburg, Wilhelm-Röpke-Straße 6
- 37 Marburg, Biegenstraße 14
- 36 Marburg, Deutschhausstraße 10
- 31 Marburg, Biegenstraße 10
- 30 Marburg, Deutschhausstraße 17a
- 23 Marburg, Wilhelm-Röpke-Straße 4
- 21 Marburg, Deutschhausstraße 12
- 20 Marburg, Barfüßerstraße 1

19 Marburg, Robert-Koch-Straße 4

...

Unfortunately, the dataset is imbalanced towards some buildings. However, we received nice and sorted by date lists of images for each building, including outdoor and indoor images. Fewer images of people and details. For example:

Address:

Marburg, Universitätsstraße 6

Additional location:

None

Dates associated:

1876–1877 Erweiterung: 1884 Erweiterung: 1926 Abbruch: 1960
um 1965

Images associated:

1884 (1884/1886)

<http://www.bildindex.de/bilder/d/fm810469>

<http://www.bildindex.de/bilder/d/fm810470>

1891 (1891/1900)

<http://www.bildindex.de/bilder/d/fm810470a>

1898 (um 1898)

<http://www.bildindex.de/bilder/d/fm415510>

1965 (um 1965/1970)

<http://www.bildindex.de/bilder/d/fm1351202>

2001 (2001)

<http://www.bildindex.de/bilder/d/fmc428865>

Two of the links give us these pictures throughout the years:

Marburg, Universitätsstraße 6

But there are disadvantages too:

- No guarantee that all objects have metadata.
- Image with a non-university-related address, which has a university building on it.
 - The solution can be to take the nearby addresses to the university ones.

3.4. NLP

In this section, we tried to use text analysis to check if we can receive better results. The results from this method weren't satisfying. But here we briefly mention:

During the project, two times we utilized Natural Language Processing, Once for knowing a rough idea about the Labels (HTML titles) which we tried to develop a Named Entity Recognition Model for which its documentation is stated in appendixes. The second time was when we wanted to indicate images between the outdoor Clusters which were done by a combination of ResNet feature extraction and K-means. The goal of this analysis was to match outdoor cluster results—based on their textual labels—with building names from a predefined dictionary.

Datasets

The project utilizes the following datasets:

Group One:

`buildings_dict.json` → `df_buildings.csv` → `df_vec_buildings.csv`

Group Two:

`outdoor_images_new.xlsx` → `dataset_Clean_whole.csv` →
`df_cluster_with_text.csv` → `df_cluster_with_text_truncated_new.csv`

Group Three:

`top_5_similar_buildings.xlsx`

Methodology

Stage 1: Merging Cluster Information with Text Labels

To obtain a dataset containing both clustering information and text labels, we used the HTML titles (text labels) from the original dataset to complete `outdoor_images_new.xlsx`, which already contained the clustering results, image links, and other metadata. No merging was performed; we simply added the corresponding text labels based on the image references.

Stage 2: Vectorization for Similarity Matching

To determine the closest matching addresses for the clustered entities, we needed to vectorize both `buildings_dict.json` and `df_cluster_with_text.csv`.

For this, we utilized SBERT (Sentence-BERT)—a sophisticated NLP technique—to generate embeddings for each entity and address. These embeddings were then concatenated into their respective Pandas DataFrames, resulting in:

- `df_vec_buildings.csv` (vectorized buildings dataset)
- `df_cluster_with_text_truncated_new.csv` (vectorized clustered entities dataset)

Stage 3: Similarity Calculation and Matching

The vectorized datasets were converted into NumPy arrays, and cosine similarity was computed to identify the most similar building addresses for each clustered entity. The results were saved in `top_5_similar_buildings.xlsx`, where each row contains:

- The name and address of the top 5 most similar buildings
- The corresponding index from `df_buildings.csv`

Filtering the Results

In order to assess the results of the similarity method, we developed a dashboard that provides an intuitive interface to explore records from the `top_5_similar_buildings.xlsx` dataset, generated by the NLP similarity model. The application allows users to interactively filter and inspect records based on similarity scores and row selection.

Conclusion

The end result was not satisfying enough due to the lack of textual information in the original dataset (and the corresponding [outdoor_images_new.xlsx](#)).

The dashboard codes can be found in the GitHub repository, and some illustrative figures are provided in the appendices.

3.5. AI-Generated Video

As a part of our presentation, we investigated AI video generation using the gathered dataset for each building and prompt engineering. We used building-specific images throughout time with two goals of achieving a video, orbiting minimally around the chosen building in an old picture, and showing the change of the building through time.

The original prompt with help of ChatGPT:

"Create a cinematic documentary-style video of a historical building evolving through time. Start with an old, low-resolution, faded photograph of the building. Progressively, with each scene, enhance the resolution, sharpness, and color fidelity step-by-step as if restoring the building through digital time. Gradually transition from black and white or sepia to full-color, high-definition images. At each transition, apply AI depth estimation and parallax effects to give the impression of slight camera movements, creating a pseudo-3D effect as if the viewer is walking around the building. Include soft atmospheric elements such as light fog, sun rays, or falling dust to evoke the passing of time. End the video with a fully restored, vibrant, high-quality image of the building shown from a slightly dynamic 3D perspective, subtly moving forward as if inviting the viewer into its story. The mood should be nostalgic, inspiring, and respectful to the building's heritage."

But the results weren't satisfying. Our original idea was that the prompt is too complicated for the machine to use both reference images from us and the prompt provided.

Through multiple tries and perfecting the prompt we achieved the best results with this prompt:

"Make a video of this building throughout time, like a timelapse

The main building shouldn't change at all, but the surroundings should change a bit

With minimal camera orbits. Keep the video documentary style."

and,

"Make a video of this building with minimal camera orbits

The main building shouldn't change at all

Keep the video documentary style”

3.6. University Building Classifier (MarburgLens)

As the final part of our project, we developed an image-classification system for recognizing and classifying photographs of the buildings at Philipps University of Marburg. This model is designed to work with the output images generated by our clustering methods, identifying which building each outdoor image belongs to.

The solution is based on transfer learning with ResNet50, fine-tuned specifically for this task. Our model's dataset combines our cleaned collection of images with precise building addresses and an additional dataset we gathered:

- **Classes:** 29 building addresses as labels.
- **Images:** Approximately 1752 total images collected manually and taken with a phone camera after recognizing and listing 29 of the buildings in the city that are University buildings.
- **Split:** 70% training, 20% validation, 10% testing.
- **Collection Conditions:** Uniform camera (Galaxy A54), with consistent lighting and weather, and similar perspectives.

It is worth mentioning that homogeneity in data collection led to high model performance in controlled evaluation.

Data preparation had the following points:

- Random resized crops (224x224 pixels).
- Random horizontal flips.
- Random rotation up to 15 degrees.
- Color jitter (brightness, contrast, saturation, hue).
- Normalization with ImageNet statistics.

Later, we trained the model with the specifications bellow:

- Model: **ResNet50** pretrained on ImageNet.
- Loss Function: **CrossEntropyLoss**.
- Optimizer: Adam optimizer with a learning rate of **1e-4**.
- Training Notebook: “02_train.ipynb”.
- Epochs: Fine-tuned over 15–20 epochs based on early performance stabilization.
- Saved Model: “resnet50_marburglens.pth”.

In the evaluation section, we used “evaluate_testset.py” and “evaluate_notebook.ipynb”.

Plots include:

- Confusion Matrix.

And final metrics are:

- **Test Accuracy: 97.56%**

- **Test Loss:** 0.0788
- **High performance** on almost all classes; minor instability in classes with very few test samples.

Our Batch image classification is implemented in “TMM_images_classification.py”. It predicts and classifies batches of images, and images with prediction confidence lower than 0.3 are moved to an “/unknown” folder. As a summary, for the code structure you can check:

- Data preparation and augmentation: “prepare_data.py / 01_prep_data.ipynb”.
- Training the model: “02_train.ipynb”.
- Single image prediction: “03_test_model.ipynb”.
- Full evaluation on the test set: “evaluate_testset.py / evaluate_notebook.ipynb”.
- Batch image classification and sorting: “TMM_images_classification.py”.

High accuracy is mainly attributed to data consistency (device, lighting, timing). The model is likely to require retraining or additional augmentation when deployed in varied real-world conditions.

Results On Original Dataset:

The batch classification script ([TMM_images_classification.py](#)) is designed to take **Outdoor Images Cluster**, and classify each image using the trained model, and then **sort the images into folders named after their predicted class**.

Given the relatively small dataset, the classification results are quite satisfactory. Below can be find a representative example of the output; the full set of results is available in the dependencies:

Universitätsstraße 6:

Handpicked Image:

Detected Images from Original Dataset:

Insights:

By expanding the dataset with varied environmental conditions and devices, it is possible to upgrade the model, but it can be considered for future work.

Above images are labeled as unknown, although they belong to the most prominent building of Marburg. It would be beneficial to also make subclasses for other famous buildings in Marburg, despite being a non-university building (such as Elisabetkirche in this case). since we know a more general model can distinguish between related classes and non related classes better. (in LLMs there are some papers stating this like [Reed et al., 2022](#))

3.7. Challenges and Solutions

- **Computational Resource Constraints:**
 - Resolved by utilizing an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4080 GPU.
- **Dataset:**
 - problems because of mistakes during the parsing of the data:

5697	http://ww	http://id.bKleiner Ho	[]	[]	["http://w	["https://www.bildindex.de/media/obj20290147/mi12656b11"]				
5698	http://ww	http://id.bKruzifix	["http://w	["https://v	["http://w	["https://v	http://id.bMax Komr	[]	[]	["http:
5699	http://ww	http://id.bPorträt eir	[]	[]	["http://w	["https://www.bildindex.de/media/obj20728393/mi02129f12"]				

- Problems in cases when semicolons were a part of the textual description:

15215	http://ww	http://id.bTreis an de	["http://w	["https://v	[]					
15216	http://ww	http://id.bTreis an de	["http://w	["https://v	[]					
15217	http://ww	http://id.b"Treis an d Stallunger Zehntsche Stallunger Zehntsche Amts- unc Entwurf Aufriss"	["http://w	["https://v	[]					
15218	http://ww	http://id.bTreis an de	["http://w	["https://v	[]					
15219	http://ww	http://id.bTreis an de	["http://w	["https://v	[]					

- Other unidentified problems after parsing

9059 http://www.bildindex.de/media/obj32060654/mi0
9060 http://www.bildindex.de/bilder/d/fmd10037715" "http://www.bildindex.de/bilder/c
9061 61"" ""http://www.bildindex.de/media/obj20269517/fmd10037715" "https://www.bildindex.de/media/obj2026
9062 ia/obj20269517/mi12610g03" "https://www.bildindex.de/medi
9063 "https://v,
9064 http://www.bildindex.de/media/obj20269517/mi0

- Resolved after a couple of trial-and-error file-opening and working with regular expressions, and images were saved into the repository
 - Unfortunately, there were many of them not related to the project, but which were used for the classification task
 - Noise in data is managed by removing irrelevant objects and prioritizing exterior building images.
 - **Taxonomy Creation:**
 - High number of clusters.
 - Proposed using LLMs (e.g., ChatGPT) to name clusters, ensuring structured and supervised AI usage.
 - Making sure LLM has done a trustworthy job by cross-checking manually via human observation.
-

4. Results

1. Optimized Dataset:

- 36981 images included, after cleaning and preprocessing.

2. Clustering Outcomes:

- Detailed clusters with less than 1,000 images each, facilitating human interpretation.

3. Visualization:

- Clustered images are separated into folders (0 to 99) for better review.
- Proposed use of visualization tools for public engagement.
- Creating a thumbnail for each cluster
- Using the metadata of our dataset to create AI-generated videos with two goals:

1. Orbiting around a building in an old picture
2. Showing the change of buildings through time

4. CSV format:

- Structured container of all objects, images, labels, and clusters in .csv format

5. University Building Classifier:

- A classifier trained over a ground truth dataset consisting of both old images from the MVP dataset and 1900 building images taken by the team. Labels are Marburg University buildings and focused on 29 of them.
-

5. Ideas for Future Projects

1. Enhanced Clustering:

- Sub-clustering within existing clusters to refine results further.
- Hierarchical clustering: choosing a certain number of clusters, making a new Sub-Dataset, and performing clustering on it.
- Integrating architectural style recognition to improve clustering accuracy.

2. NER and Text Analysis:

- Combine map data (e.g., OpenStreetMap) for geo-referencing objects.

3. Taxonomy Refinement:

- Employ advanced vision-language models (e.g., InternVL2) for supervised taxonomy creation.
- Develop hierarchical labeling methods to explore semantic relationships.

4. Image-Text Integration:

- Explore multimodal approaches to link images with textual descriptions.
- Investigate segmentation techniques for texts discussing multiple objects.

5. Data Augmentation:

- Incorporate synthetic data generation to address class imbalance.

6. **Architectural Research:**

- Collaborate with domain experts to validate clusters, enhance interpretations, and create storylines.

7. **Public Engagement:**

- Develop an interactive map or timeline using clustered data.
 - Organize exhibitions showcasing historical findings.
 - Developing AI video models, showing Marburg through history
-

6. Conclusion

The "Time Machine Marburg" project has laid the groundwork for leveraging AI in historical research. By clustering and analyzing thousands of historical images, we have created a structured dataset that offers immense potential for future studies. Despite challenges, the results underscore the feasibility of applying machine learning to cultural heritage datasets, paving the way for innovative research and public engagement initiatives.

7. Contribution Statement

Eva Kvindt:

- - Have done coordination role, including organizing meeting, distribution of the tasks and communication (within the team, Prof. Bell, AILab)
- - Dataset understanding and cleaning (EDA)
- - Coding of feature extraction and classification model
- - Prompt engineering for creating taxonomy with ChatGPT
- - Metadata scrapping and its further exploration as well as usage for image classification and timeline sorting
- - Developing mockups for future storyline presentation
- - Collecting of ground truth from Open Sources

- - Coding and delivering of structured and cleaned set of datasets for images, object, titles and clusters with the relation-database structure provided

Soroush Daftarian:

- -Implemented a feature extraction method using a Variational Autoencoder (VAE) to map image data into a latent space for clustering.
- -Developed a Named Entity Recognition (NER) model to extract entities from the dataset labels.
- -Executed prompt-based workflows using ChatGPT to generate taxonomies from clusters of image thumbnails
- -Applied a Sentence-BERT (SBERT) model to vectorize labels from an outdoor dataset and a dictionary of university buildings addresses, and built an interactive dashboard to visualize cosine similarity results.
- -Collected and photographed 1752 images of 29 university buildings and curated a multi-class classification-ready dataset, published on Hugging Face.
- -Developed MarburgLens, a ResNet50-based classification model to identify any of the 29 university buildings from the Outdoors_Cluster dataset.
- -Edited and completed the final documentation for the project.

Hamidreza Khoshvaghti:

- Communication management through the project and team management between teammates, keeping the Trello updated, writing and storing the meeting minutes.
- Ideation and finalizing the MVP,
- Compressing the dataset from 11GB to 500MB, detecting possible bugs in data reshape and fixing it in the resulted dataset.
- Using ResNET50 and clustering, procedure design and ideation on how to conduct
- Designing different clustering experiments and the execution of all
- Saving processor runtime via pre-compression of the dataset and correct pickling of features.
- Re-structuring the dataset into separate folders after each clustering.
- Preparation of thumbnails for each cluster to be used for creating our dataset's Taxonomy.
- Prompt engineering for better results from ChatGPT.
- Using ChatGPT and prompting to extract the clusters for outdoor images from the dataset.
- Comparison and scoring for outdoor selection process from our taxonomy between AI and human agents.
- Collection and structuring of all information from GitHub, Trello, meeting minutes, and the Telegram group.
- Creating the final documentation for the project and refining it through feedback collection from team members.
- AI Videos: Prompt engineering, using different Generative AI tools, collecting the right images from the dataset, and creation of all AI videos for the final presentation

8. Appendices

1. **GitHub Repository:** <https://github.com/KvindtEva/Time-Machine-Marburg>
2. **Hugging Face Dataset:** This dataset contains high-resolution photographs of 29 university buildings in Marburg, Germany. Each image is labeled with the building name, making it suitable for multi-class image classification tasks focused on the project Time Machine Marburg.
<https://huggingface.co/datasets/soroshdft/marburg-university-buildings>

3. **Clustering Visualization:**
 - a. **Thumbnail Images of Clusters:**

some cluster Thumbnail images are reported here:

figure of Cluster 11, the name which is generated by LLM Taxonomy Generation method for this cluster : “Historical Portraits”

the Link to all Clustering Thumbnail images: [here](#)

b. map of 100 Clusters:

figure of the map of 100 clustering results

4. Classification Results (MarburgLens subproject):

Biegenstraße 14:

Handpicked Image:

Detected Image from Original Dataset:

Biegenstraße 12:

Handpicked Image:

Detected Image from Original Dataset:

Universitätsstraße 6:

Handpicked Image:

Detected Image from Original dataset: **Wrongly detected:**

As it is obvious, the above image belongs to Biegenstraße 10 but wrongly detected as Law Library, Universitätsstraße 6.

Universitätsstraße 7:

Handpicked Image:

Detected Image from Original Dataset:

5. Variational Autoencoder :

the link of implemented VAE in github: [here](#)

6. Natural Language Processing:

a. Named Entity Recognition:

```
↩ Caption 1: Lauenhain (Kreis Hainichen), Fahnenträger eines internationalen Zeltlagers
- Lauenhain: LOC (Score: 1.0000)
- Hainichen: LOC (Score: 1.0000)

Caption 2: Fenster (Bauelement)
No entities found.

Caption 3: Kassel, Infanteriekasernen an der Königsstraße, Bestandsaufnahme, Situationsplan
- Kassel: LOC (Score: 1.0000)
- Königsstraße: LOC (Score: 1.0000)

Caption 4: Waldeck, Domäne, Wohnhaus, Umbaumentwurf, Aufrisse
- Waldeck: LOC (Score: 1.0000)

Caption 5: Kassel, Opernhaus (Altes Hoftheater), Aborte im Flügelgebäude, Entwurf, Grundriss
- Kassel: LOC (Score: 1.0000)
- Altes Hoftheater: LOC (Score: 1.0000)

Caption 6: Mengsberg, Oberförster-Etablisement, Bauaufnahmen, Grundrisse, Aufrisse, Querschnitte, Längsschnitte und Lageplan
- Mengsberg: LOC (Score: 1.0000)

Caption 7: Mengsberg, Oberförster-Etablisement, Bauaufnahmen, Grundrisse, Aufrisse, Querschnitte, Längsschnitte und Lageplan Mengsberg, Oberförster-
- Mengsberg: LOC (Score: 1.0000)
- Mengsberg: LOC (Score: 1.0000)
- Mengsberg: LOC (Score: 1.0000)
```

- As suggested, we tried to make a NER algorithm specifically for Marburg Entities
- First, we used an NER model for the German Language, SpaCy. And then, we added RegEx patterns to obtain and check the basic result:

```

Analyzing label 2:
Text: Fenster (Bauelement)
No Marburg-specific entities found.
-----

Analyzing label 3:
Text: Kassel, Infanteriekasernen an der Königsstraße, Bestandsaufnahme, Situationsplan
Entities found:
- Kassel (0:6) - LOC
- Königsstraße (34:46) - LOC
- Bestandsaufnahme (48:64) - LOC
- Situationsplan (66:80) - LOC
-----

Analyzing label 4:
Text: Waldeck, Domäne, Wohnhaus, Umbauentwurf, Aufrisse
Entities found:
- Waldeck (0:7) - LOC
-----

Analyzing label 5:
Text: Kassel, Opernhaus (Altes Hoftheater), Aborte im Flügelgebäude, Entwurf, Grundriss
Entities found:
- Kassel (0:6) - LOC
- Opernhaus (8:17) - LOC
- Altes Hoftheater (19:35) - LOC
-----

Analyzing label 6:
Text: Mengersberg, Oberförster-Etablissement, Bauaufnahmen, Grundrisse, Aufrisse, Querschnitte, Längsschnitte und Lage
Entities found:
- Mengersberg (0:9) - MARBURG_RELATED
- Mengersberg (0:9) - LOC
- Oberförster-Etablissement (11:36) - LOC
- Querschnitte (74:86) - LOC

```

```

# Define Marburg-related patterns
marburg_patterns = [
    r'\bMarburg\b',
    r'\bMengersberg\b',
    r'\bMarburg-Biedenkopf\b',
    r'\bLandkreis Marburg\b',
    r'\bPhilipps-Universität\b'
]

```

The results for the tags of the whole city:

```

Analyzing label 14:
Text: Mengersberg, Oberförster-Etablissement, Bauaufnahme
Entities found:
- Mengersberg (0:9) - LOCATION
- Oberförster-Etablissement (11:36) - BUILDING
- Bauaufnahmen (38:50) - DOCUMENT_TYPE
- Aufrisse (64:72) - DOCUMENT_TYPE
- Querschnitte (74:86) - DOCUMENT_TYPE
- Längsschnitte (88:101) - DOCUMENT_TYPE
- Lageplan (106:114) - DOCUMENT_TYPE
- Mengersberg (115:124) - LOCATION
- Oberförster-Etablissement (126:151) - BUILDING
- Bauaufnahmen (153:165) - DOCUMENT_TYPE
- Aufrisse (179:187) - DOCUMENT_TYPE
- Querschnitte (189:201) - DOCUMENT_TYPE
- Längsschnitte (203:216) - DOCUMENT_TYPE
- Lageplan (221:229) - DOCUMENT_TYPE
- Mengersberg (230:239) - LOCATION
- Oberförster-Etablissement (241:266) - BUILDING
- Försterwohnung (268:282) - BUILDING

```

```

Analyzing label 10:
Text: Mengersberg, Oberförster-Etablissement, Bauaufnahmen, Grundrisse,
Entities found:
- Mengersberg (0:9) - LOCATION
- Oberförster-Etablissement (11:36) - BUILDING
- Bauaufnahmen (38:50) - DOCUMENT_TYPE
- Aufrisse (64:72) - DOCUMENT_TYPE
- Querschnitte (74:86) - DOCUMENT_TYPE
- Längsschnitte (88:101) - DOCUMENT_TYPE
- Lageplan (106:114) - DOCUMENT_TYPE
- Mengersberg (115:124) - LOCATION
- Oberförster-Etablissement (126:151) - BUILDING
- Bauaufnahmen (153:165) - DOCUMENT_TYPE
- Aufrisse (179:187) - DOCUMENT_TYPE
- Querschnitte (189:201) - DOCUMENT_TYPE
- Längsschnitte (203:216) - DOCUMENT_TYPE
- Lageplan (221:229) - DOCUMENT_TYPE
- Mengersberg (230:239) - LOCATION
- Oberförster-Etablissement (241:266) - BUILDING
- Försterwohnung (268:282) - BUILDING
- Grundriss (309:318) - DOCUMENT_TYPE

```

And for the university tags which didn't lead to good results:

Analyzing label 67:
 Text: Waldeck, Domäne, Wohnhaus, Umbautentwurf, Schnitt
 No university-related entities found.

Analyzing label 68:
 Text: Rostock, Jahrmarkt, Karussell
 No university-related entities found.

Analyzing label 69:
 Text: Projekt Kunst am Bau für das Studentenzentrum der Philipps-Universität Marburg auf den Lahnbergen
 University-related entities found:
 - Philipps-Universität Marburg (50:78) - UNIVERSITY
 - Universität Marburg (59:78) - UNIVERSITY

Analyzing label 70:
 Text: Markttreiben nahe der El-Ashar-Universität
 No university-related entities found.

the link to github codes of this part of project: [here](#)

b. dashboard of Cosine Similarity and Outdoor vectorized dataset:

The figure of NLP model Dashboard, This interactive dashboard lets users explore NLP-generated building similarity results from the *top_5_similar_buildings.xlsx* file. Users can filter entries by cosine similarity threshold and select which rows to display. The results are shown in a dynamic table with building names, addresses, similarity scores, and clickable webpage links—all updating in real-time based on the filters.

7. AI generated Videos:

The link to the AI Generated Videos : [here](#)